

Moisture-density test

Purpose						Specimens		fiber-stabilized carbide-slag-solidified soil			
Date						2021.5.12					
test basis		JTG E40-2007									
equipment		electric compaction device(TG-01); drying case(TG-07); electronic balance(TG-10);									
Hammer quality (kg)		4.5	Number of hits per layer	27	drop (mm)	450					
test times		1		2		3		4		5	
ρ_d	tube volume (cm ³)	994.93		994.93		990.18		987.01		987.01	
	Tube weight (g)	1945.50		1944.90		2133.40		1971.10		2134	
	Tube + wet soil quality (g)	3790.40		3878.80		4053.30		3862.30		3900.3	
	wet soil quality (g)	1844.90		1933.90		1919.90		1891.20		1766.30	
	ρ (g/cm ³)	1.854		1.944		1.939		1.916		1.790	
	ρ_d (g/cm ³)	1.64		1.68		1.65		1.60		1.62	
ω	NO.	19	142	41	51	22	94	68	132	94	26
	Box quality (g)	12.10	12.00	10.83	12.37	11.57	11.71	11.14	11.99	11.73	10.51
	Box + wet soil quality (g)	111.10	87.60	77.53	72.10	70.30	73.07	72.89	70.31	81.51	70.99
	Box + dry soil quality (g)	101.02	79.89	69.26	65.19	62.57	65.11	64.10	62.10	75.63	65.86
	water mass (g)	10.08	7.71	8.27	6.91	7.73	7.96	8.79	8.21	5.88	5.13
	dry soil quality (g)	88.92	67.89	58.43	52.82	51.00	53.40	52.96	50.11	63.90	55.35
	ω (%)	11.34	11.36	14.15	13.08	15.16	14.91	16.60	16.38	9.20	9.27
	average moisture content (%)	11.35		13.62		15.03		16.49		9.24	
ρ_{dmax} (g/cm ³)	1.68				OMC (%)		13.6				